

**DETECTION OF MALARIA CELL USING IMAGE DATASET WITH
CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK**

A

PROJECT PRESENTED

BY

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COMPUTER SCIENCE.**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project work entitled “Detection of Malaria Cell using image Dataset with Convolutional Neural Network” is a collection of my original research work and it has not been presented for any other qualification anywhere. Information from other sources (published or unpublished) has been duly acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION PAGE

This is to certify that this project work “Detection of Malaria Cell using image Dataset with Convolutional Neural Network” was carried out by Ebri Victor Iwara with Matric Number 17283102, meets the regulations governing the award of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science of the University of Abuja and it is approved for its contribution to scientific Knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to ALMIGHTY GOD who through his infinite mercy, love, grace, and kindness has been my source of inspiration till the end of this project work, and my wonderful and supporting Friend, Segun Solomon Oladinran.

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I give all thanks to God for the gift of life, infinite love, and the successful completion of this project. My greatest motivators are my brother, Mr Daniel Ebri and Sister, Miss Joy Ebri. I appreciate your words of encouragement and all of the daily prayers you have said for me. Thank you so much for always being there for me! I appreciate all of my family members that supported me. My deepest appreciation to my wonderful professors, who have accompanied my studies for the last four years, and to my supervisor, Prof. Owolabi Olumide for all of her support, care, and commitment in guiding me through the composition of my project, you inspired me to become a better professional every day. Thanks to my friends especially Idris Bishop and my colleagues who gave me the support I needed to get here.

ABSTRACT

Malaria is currently one of the most deadly diseases in the world. While there are different treatment methods for the disease, the search for new drugs against malaria is still a very important area of research. One of the main challenges in manufacturing drugs against malaria is efficiently evaluating the performance of the drugs on the parasites since it requires, amongst others, precise measurements of the parasite growth-stages as well as their counts in blood smear images. The current gold-standard for making such detail diagnosis is manual microscopy which is tedious. This research showed that convolutional neural networks can be used to identify the different growth- cycle stages of Plasmodium parasites, even in situations where there is little data. Employing a variety of data augmentation techniques and transfer learning, a semantic segmentation model was built to discriminate between trophozoites, gametocytes and normal red blood cells with an accuracy of 85.86 percent in 353 Giemsa-stained thin blood smears. The results showed that it is possible to perform dense predictions on Giemsa-stained thin blood smears using convolutional neural networks.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The world's population is at risk of malaria, a dangerous infectious disease caused by the Plasmodium parasite. Literally, a child under five years dies of malaria every two minutes. About 429,000 people died from the disease in 2015; sub-Saharan Africa alone accounted for 90 percent of all deaths (WHO, 2017). These statistics might just be a microcosm of the problems malaria poses to societies as a lot more cases go unreported. These are very shocking statistics, considering that different treatment methods for the disease exist. Besides the loss of lives, malaria creates other numerous economic and social problems to many countries, especially to developing countries where the disease is endemic. This infectious disease called malaria is a parasitic illness caused by female anopheles mosquitoes carrying the plasmodium parasite. In severe instances, red blood cells infected with the plasmodium parasite can cause symptoms such as headaches, seizures, coma, and death. Urgent and reliable diagnosis and early treatment of malaria is among the most effective ways of fighting the disease, together with better treatments and mosquito control (Mahdieh et al., 2018).

The assessment of micro-blood smear images is still the standard method for diagnosing malaria. It has the ability to identify parasitic organism species, measure parasite intensity, and evaluate the efficacy of anti-malarial treatment, among other things. Regrettably, due to the high costs of training professionals in our traditional institutions, malaria-affected areas frequently lack qualified personnel who can conduct high-quality microscopy examinations (Hang et al., 2020). Diagnosis of malaria can be difficult, where malaria is not endemic anymore, health-care providers may not be familiar with the disease. Clinicians while examining a malaria patient tend to forget to consider malaria as a potential disease and hence don't suggest the necessary diagnostic tests. Detecting parasites while examining blood smears under the microscope requires experience, which the laboratorians may lack and thus fail to detect (Mohd et al., 2020).

In some malaria-endemic areas, a large section of the population is infected by the parasites but are still not ill or sick. Such carriers have the malaria infection but they have developed just enough immunity not to get the malaria illness or to show any symptoms in their system. In that case, finding malaria parasites in an ill person doesn't necessarily mean that malaria is the root cause of the person's illness or the parasites is solely responsible for the illness. The proposed system would sense the presence of malaria parasites on a regular blood-smear slide. A phone camera can be attached to the microscope's ocular to take the blood smear photographs and then analyze it. Traditional malaria detection approaches are very time consuming and they may produce inaccurate reports due to human errors, and are laborious for extensive diagnoses. Based on the weaknesses of the state-of-the-art solution, a Deep learning technique is being proposed (Faza et al., 2021).

Deep learning techniques are now generally used for image classification and medical image analysis. It has been a proven method which increases the performance in any field. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), a type of deep neural networks, is essentially considered for research in the computer vision field. The deep architecture of CNN is its main power. The convolutional layer in the CNN works as an automatic feature extractor that extracts hidden and important features. Extracted features are passed to a fully connected neural network that performs classification images by maximizing the probability scores (Çinar et al., 2020).

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Malaria in a human being is caused by four main species of the Plasmodium parasite: Plasmodium falciparum, Plasmodium vivax, Plasmodium malariae, and Plasmodium ovale. Of these four major species, Plasmodium falciparum is the most prevalent parasite in Africa. It is also the species responsible for the most severe form of malaria in human beings (WHO 2017). Parasites have four major growth-cycle stages and they are sporozoites, merozoites, trophozoites and gametocytes (Srinivas, 2015). There are other stages of the parasites which occur outside the human body. As part of the measures to mitigate the impact of malaria on the progress of societies, the World Health Organization (WHO) directed an estimated US\$ 2.7 billion in 2016 in funding for malaria control and elimination research projects (WHO, 2017). World Health Organization's efforts have mainly been in vector control which has yielded the greatest success in controlling malaria so far (Karunamoorthi et al., 2011). However, while vector control measures are effective in reducing the transmission of the disease from infected people to uninfected people, they are not effective at helping to eradicate the Plasmodium parasites. This is

largely due to vector resistance. The female *Anopheles* mosquito, the main vector of the disease, is known for its ability to build resistance against control measures such as its resistance to insecticides in sub-Saharan Africa (WHO, 2017). Consequently, increasingly more complex control measures are required to prevent the spread of the disease. The traditional method testing of malaria takes a long time to get the result, and as this is a more prevalent disease in areas where conflict and war occur. In such case, the prevalence of malaria increases. For reasons such as poor shelter, lack of physical activity, lack of sanitation, lack of health education and the rapid spread of the disease. The message was motivated by the lack of adequate measures to control malaria. There are a large number of people infected with this disease worldwide and the disease has caused the death of many people if we are to examine people's concerns that we need a time period to perform tests at the level of all community samples. malaria is a mosquito-borne disease caused by a plasmodium parasite transmitted by the bite of infected mosquitoes.

Worldwide accepted light microscopy technique is used by the practitioners for the diagnosis of malaria. The conventional light microscopy for malaria diagnosis uses thick and thin stained blood smears for diagnoses. Microscopy is well adapted in areas which are highly prone to malaria. The major drawback of this approach is its dependence on skilled technicians, of which there is a critical shortage. A nationwide study in Ghana found 1.72 microscopes per 100,000 population, but only .85 trained laboratory staff per 100,000 population (Chakrabortva et al., 2015). This results in a delay in an inaccurate diagnosis. Most of the time, diagnosis is often made based on clinical signs and symptoms alone, which is error-prone and this inaccurate diagnosis leads to higher mortality, drug resistance, and the economic burden of buying unnecessary drugs. Early and accurate malaria diagnosis and prompt treatment can cure a patient and save many lives by preventing severe malaria cases. All around the world, there are millions of people who still lacking access to malaria prevention and treatment. Therefore, there is a need for a reliable alternative which will help to provide access to high-quality diagnosis routinely that is currently unavailable. This research focuses on designing an accurate malaria diagnosis model that can be implemented without any dependencies on skilled technicians and testing the model accuracy to get high-quality results. Automated image analysis software could remove the most serious limitation of the worldwide accepted microscopy method in general, dependency on human experts for diagnostic accuracy of the results. Automating the detection process means using the knowledge, the practice of conventional methods, and implementing it to get fast and efficient result.

1.3 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main aim of this project is to address the challenges in the existing system by automating the process of malaria detection using an image dataset with a convolutional neural network. This project aims to

- fill that gap by providing techniques to identify and count the growth-cycle stages of Plasmodium parasites on digitized images.

The main objective of the research is

- to improve the efficiency of developing antimalarial drugs.

To achieve this objective, the project employs convolutional neural networks (CNN), a variant of deep learning to classify and count growth-cycle stages of Plasmodium falciparum parasites on Giemsa-stained images.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The process of developing anti-malarial drugs can be described broadly as an iterative assessment of the effectiveness of some chemicals at killing Plasmodium parasites. That is, proposed anti-malarial drugs are applied to Plasmodium parasites and the number of parasites that are killed by the drugs is assessed. In this process, counting the number of parasites accurately is crucial in the assessment of the proposed drug samples. Besides assessing how the parasites react in general to anti-malarial drugs, it is equally important to measure the impact of the drugs on the different growth-cycle stages. For instance, instead of killing the parasites, partially effective drugs can increase the production of gametocytes, the sexual stage of the parasite (White, 2008). Thus, accurately identifying the growth-cycle stages of the parasites is also necessary for discriminating the performance of different proposed anti-malaria drugs.

1.5 SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The limitations of vector control measures call for preventive measures as well as control measures to fight the disease. In this regard, good anti-malarial drugs have been identified as quintessential in the ultimate eradication of malaria (White, 2008). Research and manufacture of effective anti-malarial drugs is therefore important, especially if WHO is to achieve its target of reducing malaria deaths by at least 90 percent by 2030 (WHO, 2017). However, the multiple

incidences of drug resistance such as the Plasmodium parasites resistance to chloroquine in the 1950s (Wellems et al., 2001), make the research and development of anti-malarial drugs a challenging task (Ojha, 2015). Nonetheless, research for anti-malarial drugs can be conducted effectively with the right tools, such as with automated systems, as discussed later in this paper.

1.6 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted for the implementation of this study is Structured System Analysis and Design Methodology (SSADM). This methodology was selected because it allows the researcher to design the system by creating objects which are able to interact with each other and accomplish the required aim. Also, it allows the researcher to depict the system easily with the help of special diagrams which includes use case diagrams, activity diagrams, and class diagrams. The steps involved in this kind of methodology are requirements specification; Analysis; Design; Implementation (coding); Testing; Maintenance

Deep learning models are reliable and easily scalable with a higher accuracy rate. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have proved to be really effective in a wide variety of computer vision tasks. Convolutional Neural Networks transform input image volume into an output volume holding a class label. In Convolutional modeling, there is no need for feature extraction and feature engineering as extracting the features with the most variance like which feature holds more importance. CNN models take the images as an input, the image is passed on different layers of the CNN model which is discussed in further sections. This makes Convolutional Neural Network an optimal approach for diagnosing Malaria using patient blood cell images.

In this project work, the researcher attempted to answer two research questions:

- Compare models to find which Convolutional Neural Network between RESNET50 and VGG-19 performs better on the malaria dataset?
- Is there any difference in the Convolutional Neural Network performance measured on the malaria dataset before and after applying preprocessing techniques like data augmentation, stain normalization and standardization.

1.7 CHAPTER LAYOUT

It contains five chapters, Chapter one talks about the overall purpose of detecting malaria cell using data set with convolutional neural network.

Chapter two is the literature review which gives a detailed of previous research that has been conducted on this study.

Chapter three explains the methods, procedures, strategies and design used in the research.

Chapter four is the result of the analysis and the implementation of the research. Chapter five is the summary, conclusion and recommendation of this research.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most infectious and a highly transmissible disease caused by a blood parasite which belongs to genre of Plasmodium is Malaria. Considering the traditional and the general microscopy method, which is “The Gold Standard” for malaria detection, has been proven to be inconsistent because the process requires significant amount of time and the results are difficult to reproduce as and when required. Malaria is causing a serious global health issue, and the appraised process is of high significance. The system developed here represents a model that uses image processing techniques and algorithms that are, definite, rapid and cost-effective. Datasets consisting of images of affected and non-affected erythrocytes are collected, preprocessed, closely connected features are extracted from the acquired images and finally, it is confirmed whether the sample image is infected or not based on the features that are extracted from them. A set of characteristics depending on the features are suggested, and the performance from that created a database of the features on the erythrocyte (Neha et al., 2019).

2.1.1 Malaria and Plasmodium Parasites

This study involved only Plasmodium falciparum because it is the most prevalent species of Plasmodium in Africa. Consequently, the brief review of Plasmodium parasites as presented in this chapter is in the context of the species called P.falciparum. In addition, to this chapter and in the rest of the project, Plasmodium parasites can be used loosely to refer to P. falciparum. Finally, for brevity, parasites are used in place of Plasmodium parasites whenever the meaning is unambiguous. As discussed in chapter one, there are four major stages of growth of Plasmodium parasites in human beings. Sporozoites are the first stage of the parasites in humans. When matured, they rupture releasing merozoites into the blood stream. Merozoites then invade Red Blood Cells and produce trophozoites through asexual reproduction. The trophozoites develop into schizonts which also burst and release merozoites and gametocytes. The merozoites re- invade other RBCs while the gametocytes wait to be transferred into a mosquito during a blood meal by the later (Srinivas, 2015).

Although gametocytes do not cause malaria infection directly, they aid in the transmission of the disease. Therefore, it is important for new therapeutics to be able to target all the life stages of the parasite (Delves et al., 2012). The ability to get an accurate count of each of the parasite life stages is essential in testing these therapeutics. The various stages of the parasite have different shapes and

survival mechanisms (Srinivas, 2015). Gametocytes have crescent shapes like a half-moon. Trophozoites have circular shapes and are often located completely inside RBCs. The unique characteristics of the different growth-cycle stages of the parasites can be revealed through staining. Images of trophozoites and gametocytes are shown in Figure 2.1.

(Figure 2.1: *Plasmodium* parasites growth-cycle stages)

The red marking depicts a gametocyte in its advanced stages. Gametocytes generally have elongated shapes as shown in the picture

2.1.2 Staining

Staining is a technique which is often used to enhance visualization and identification of *Plasmodium* parasites in manual microscopy. A correctly stained blood smear is crucial in malaria diagnosis, especially when precise identification of growth-cycle stages is desired (Gonzales, 2016). Although there are other staining substances and techniques such as Leishman (Sathpathi et al., 2014) and DAPI (Moon et al., 2013), Giemsa is the standard and most reliable stain for all forms of blood smears. Examples of Giemsa- stained images (thin and thick blood smears) are shown in Figure 2.2 below. Thick blood smears can detect a few parasites in a blood film. However, their preparation process destroys the RBCs. Hence, thick smears are mostly used for *Yes* or *No* diagnoses. On the other hand, thin blood smears as shown in Figure 2.2b preserve the structure of the RBCs and the parasites. This property makes thin smears the suitable method for diagnosing malaria when the species or the life-cycle of the parasites is needed. This project used thin blood smears for the parasites growth-cycle stages detection.

2.2 MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR AUTOMATED MALARIA DIAGNOSIS

Image processing and pattern recognition has been at the center of research in computer vision with regards to improving the accuracy of identifying Plasmodium parasites in digitized images (Bibin et al., 2017; Rosado, Correia, Elias, & Cardoso, 2016; Nanoti et al., 2016; Park, Rinehart, Walzer, Ashley Chi, & Wax, 2016; Mehrjou, Abbasian, and Izadi, 2013). These algorithms work by learning patterns in mostly labeled data. They then use the knowledge gathered to make informed predictions about the presence or absence of parasites in datasets the algorithms have not seen before. These approaches yield consistent diagnosis and have been shown to even outperform human beings in some classification tasks (He, Zhang, Ren, and Sun, 2015). Therefore, if applied properly, computer aided malaria diagnosis can address the problems associated with manual microscopy.

(Figure 2.2: Example images of Giemsa-stained blood smears)

- Thick blood smear - in the thick blood smear, all the cells including the structure of the parasites are destroyed. It is easy to prepare thick smears compared to thin smears but they cannot be used for very informative diagnosis.
- Thin blood smear - in the thin blood smear, all the red blood cells, as well as the true form of the parasites are maintained. Also, thin blood smears expose artifacts such as platelets and chemical compounds.

One of the factors contributing to the success of computer vision applications is the availability of large labeled data for training the algorithms (Brynjolfsson & Andrew, 2017). However, achieving optimum performance of the algorithms on the data is not trivial. It typically involves making many design choices about the algorithms as well as the formatting and presentation of the data. Data preprocessing is the first step in many approaches with regards to data preparation tasks.

Preprocessing tasks usually involve tasks such as data cleaning and other transformations such as conversion to grayscale. Preprocessing is important in computer vision applications for the identification and counting of Plasmodium parasites on digitized stained images. This is because the images usually contain other foreign objects such as platelets which are also stained during slide preparation. Removing these artifacts before classification improves the accuracy of the diagnosis. It is also crucial to perform other preprocessing functions such as luminance normalizations (Díaz, González, & Romero, 2009) to reduce the impact of illuminations of the images on the performance of the algorithms. In research laboratories, however, the problem of foreign objects on images is minimal since the data is often prepared from cultured samples.

The color and morphological properties (shape) of the objects in the images are the primary parameters of interest to the machine learning algorithms. Therefore, it is important to use good feature generation techniques to extract the relevant properties of the data. However, this is only an important task when using traditional machine learning algorithms⁴. Research in computer vision malaria diagnosis using traditional machine learning algorithms also generally convert red green blue (RGB) images to grayscale (Rosado et al., 2016) to reduce the complexity of the images. Some of these approaches in automated malaria diagnosis are reviewed in the succeeding paragraphs.

Due to the large number of studies in automated malaria diagnosis which have appeared in several literature in the last ten years, it is impractical to conduct a detail review of all the proposals. As such, this section presents only an overview of a few of the proposed systems. However, a full review of intelligent malaria diagnosis systems can be found at (Poostchi *et al.* 2018).

(Ghosh et al., 2014) developed a method for estimating parasitaemia in thin blood smears using mainly statistical and mathematical techniques. This involved computing the features of the images such as centroids, mean and variance of the different regions under the assumption that the images were positive RGB images. They then fed these features to the algorithm for classification. Although Gosh *et al.* did not include any performance metrics in their paper, they demonstrated that parasitaemia in thin blood smears can be measured automatically using computers. However, the performance of the algorithm relied on the good engineering of the features. It is difficult to construct the features manually. Finally, their approach cannot be used for estimating parasitaemia in images which may not have parasites at all.

Unlike Gosh *et al.*, Bibin *et al.* used deep belief networks pre-trained with Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBMs) to detect malaria parasites in digital blood smear images. Their approach resulted in an F-score of 89.66 percent and a specificity of 97.60 percent on a binary classification

of images into parasites and non-parasites. These scores are indications that deep networks can classify parasites in digitized images with high accuracies. Support vector machines (SVMs) are by far the most used machine learning algorithms for malaria diagnosis studies due to their simplicity (Rosado et al., 2016; Pinkaew et al., 2015; Linder et al., 2014; Savkare, 2011). Like the method employed by Gosh *et al.*, SVMs require explicit feature generation from the images. Pinkaew *et al.* for instance, extracted the kurtosis, mean, standard deviation, skewness and entropy from four color channels of the images which were then projected to the SVMs to classify between *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Plasmodium vivax* species. Like DBNs, SVMs perform well on non-linear data due to their ability to transform lower dimensional data into higher dimensions using kernels. However, they are limited by the fact that they can typically only perform binary classification tasks. Adapting SVMs for multi-class classification problems such as the classification of the growth-cycle stages of *Plasmodium* parasites is timeinefficient and prone to errors.

Moon *et al.* (2013) developed an approach to identify the various growth-cycle stages of malaria parasites as well as discriminate between dead and active parasites in drug- treated samples. Their algorithm used the intensity of DAPI-stained parasite nuclei spots in fluorescence images to identify infected RBCs. The algorithm also detected and quantized threedifferent growth-cycle stages of the *Plasmodium* parasite (rings, trophozoites, schizonts). The gametocyte stage was not considered in this study. In computing the total number of RBCs per image field, the average area of isolated RBCs is first calculated. Afterwards, the number of RBCs in each cluster is estimated from the ratio of the area of the cluster to the average areaof each RBC. The combined total of the isolated RBCs and sum is an average of the ~~precision and recall~~ values. Precision is the number of true positives divided by the number of positives predicted by the classifier. Recall is a measure of the sensitivity of the classifier. Specificity is a measure of the true negative rate. It denotes the percentage of true negatives were correctly classified of RBCs in all clustered regions is taken as the definitive RBCs count of the image field under consideration. This approach saves a lot of time in estimating the RBCs count since no work is done to untangle clustered RBCs. The diagnosis process involved identifying infected RBCs and then estimating the parasite density. The proposed method achieved a 100 percent accuracy when tested on a dataset of nine images. However, the number of images was too small to consider the performance of the algorithm conclusive.

A genetic programming algorithm has also been used for the classification of *Plasmodium* parasites on thick-blood smear images (Purnama, Rahmanti, and Purnomo, 2013). Purnama et al. provided a more complete model compared to the studies above. Their system included functionality for identifying the species of the *Plasmodium* parasite (*P. falciparum*, *P.vivax*, *P.ovale* and *P.malariae*)

responsible for a particular infection. The genetic algorithm approach also identified the predominant life-cycle stage (schizonts and trophozoites, gametocytes) present in the image at the time of diagnosis. Whilst their model had different phases, it also required a lot of pre-processed features. Hence, even with a classification accuracy of 94.82 percent, it is still exposed to the same problems traditional machine learning algorithms encounter at feature extraction. Other machine learning algorithms which have been used in malaria diagnosis are K-Nearest Neighbors classifiers (KNN) and linear discriminant classification (LDC) (Nanoti et al., 2016). Nanoti et al. for instance, used a two stage KNN method to identify the growth-cycle stages of the parasites with a 90.17 percent accuracy. Other researchers used more morphological techniques in the automated systems compared to those explored above (Linder et al., 2014; Kareem, Kale, & Morling, 2012). In the case of Kareem et al. (2012), they used morphological filtering to remove foreign objects from the images. Their main classification of the images was also composed of both morphological approaches and properties of the images such as color histogram and intensity. The system achieved an accuracy of 87 percent on a qualitative diagnosis of Giemsa-stained Plasmodium falciparum parasites.

Chakrabortya (2015) used unsupervised machine learning algorithms to classify Plasmodium vivax parasites in Jaswant Singh Battacharya (JSB)- stained thick blood smear images. Employing colorbased pixel discrimination methods for the classification process, the system showed 94.5 percent accuracy and 0.10 percent false positive rate on 75 images. Unsupervised machine learning techniques are particularly useful for dealing with small labeled training datasets. Other techniques such as data augmentation and transfer learning have also been proposed to deal with data sparsity.

2.3 CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR MALARIA DIAGNOSIS

The challenge with using traditional machine learning algorithms such as those in the literature discussed above is that they need hand-engineered features. Unfortunately, constructing these features is not always easy. Hand-engineering might also result in the loss of useful information to the classification task. Deep learning methods address this problem by performing end-to-end learning. That is, they learn the features from the raw data in addition to performing classification task. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are a type of deep learning specialized for image analysis. In particular, CNNs preserve the spatial structure of the images. This subsection discusses the literature in automated malariadiagnosis using convolutional neural networks.

Since Alex Krizhevsky won the ImageNet challenge in 2012 (Krizhevsky, Sutskever, & Geoffrey E., 2012) with the famous AlexNet, deep learning has been applied to a wide range of problems

including self-driving cars, speech recognition, natural language processing and disease diagnosis. (Quinn *et al.*, 2016) proposed one of the first computer vision malaria diagnosis systems using CNNs. Their approach involved annotating thick blood smears captured using a custom-made microscope smart phone adapter. The annotations were used as positive samples. They generated negative samples by randomly selecting regions of the images not intersecting any annotation. Their method obtained a 1.00 true positive rate and 0.97 precision recall on receiver operator characteristics (ROC) curves. Like most studies in malaria diagnosis, Quinn *et al.* investigated only the binary classification problem using thick blood smears. global white balancing, adaptive non-linear gray scaling and local thresholding, the proto- type application achieved acceptable accuracy in parasite quantization required for drug resistance studies. Although the application used a variety of deep learning techniques and was the first of its kind to use CNNs on large datasets (5,707,947 field-of-views), the CNNs were used for feature extraction only. Using CNNs for only feature extraction increases the complexity of the algorithm as separate models must be developed for the classification and the quantification tasks. By using thickblood films, the application does not apply to the multi-class task of parasite growth-cycle stages classification.

Gopakumar *et al.* (2017) proposed a completely automated system capable of performing quantitative malaria diagnosis. The system uses CNNs on focus stack images acquired from a US\$1500 custom-built slide scanner. By processing patches of the images, the CNNs eliminated the need for hand-engineered features. This yielded 97.6 percent sensitivity and 98.50 percent specificity accuracies for object detection in the binary classification setting. One of the main contributions of Gopakumar *et al.* is that they showed CNNs can still attain good performance by processing only patches of the image. However, conventional methods such as SVMs were used in generating the suspected patches for the CNNs to operate on. Thus the performance of the CNN was limited by the accuracy of the SVMs in generating good patches.

With a dataset of 363 images, (Penas *et al.*, 2017) obtained a 92.4 percent for Plasmodium parasite detection using CNNs. Their model also managed to discriminate between *P.falciparum* and *P.vivax* species at 87.9 percent accuracy. Penas *et al.* showed that even with small datasets CNNs can obtain good scores on malaria diagnosis tasks using data augmentation and transfer learning,. Although they used thin blood smears they focus on only binary classification. Nonetheless, they showed that CNNs can be effective on thin blood smears.

2.4 SUMMARY OF RELATED LITERATURE

Thus far, the literature shows that CNNs outperform conventional machine learning algorithms such as KNN in automated malaria diagnosis. This is because CNNs generally learn the features from the raw images which often result in effective classification. The problem with using CNNs, however, is that they often require thousands of images for good performance. Such large datasets are not commonly available especially in medical imaging. Novel techniques such as transfer learning, data augmentation and context encoding are often used for tasks where the datasets are small.

The literature also shows that using CNNs for malaria diagnosis has gained much prominence in recent years [2015 to 2018]. However, like the conventional machine learning algorithms, CNNs have mostly been applied to the binary classification task as far as malaria diagnosis is concerned. Although a few models experimented discriminating between *Plasmodium* species, no CNN-based method has been used for parasite growth-cycle identification. This research (to the best of my knowledge) is the first to investigate using CNNs for the classification and quantification of the growth-cycle stages of *P. falciparum* on thin blood smears. The novelty of this approach is that it combines the advantages of data augmentation, unsupervised pre-training and transfer learning to perform a semantic segmentation on thin blood smears given very little data. As far as I know, semantic segmentation is yet to be applied to *Plasmodium* parasites detection.

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 SYSTEM DESIGN

The methodology adopted for the implementation of this study is Structured System Analysis and Design Methodology (SSADM). This methodology is selected because it allows the researcher to design the system by creating objects which are able to interact with each other and accomplish their required aim. Also, it allows the researcher to depict the system easily with the help of special diagrams which includes use case diagrams, activity diagrams, and class diagrams. The steps involved in this kind of methodology are requirements specification;

- Analysis;
- Design;
- Implementation (coding);
- Testing;
- Maintenance.

3.1.1 neural network

Neural network is a series of algorithms that endeavors to recognize underlying relationships in a set of data through a process that mimics the way the human brain operates. In this sense, neural networks refer to systems of neurons, either organic or artificial in nature. Neural networks can adapt to changing input; so, the network generates the best possible result without needing to redesign the output criteria. neural network works similarly to the human brain's neural network. A "neuron" in a neural network is a mathematical function that collects and classifies information according to a specific architecture. The network bears a strong resemblance to statistical methods such as curve fitting and regression analysis. A neural network contains layers of interconnected nodes. Each node is a perceptron and is similar to a multiple linear regression. The perceptron feeds the signal produced by a multiple linear regression into an activation function that may be nonlinear.

3.1.2 cnn training algorithm

Convolution is represented mathematically with an asterisk * sign. If we have an input image represented as X and a filter represented with f , then the expression would be:

$$Z = X * f$$

the algorithm for the training of an image dataset is

given as thus;

Step 1: Load the input images in a variable (say X)

Step 2: Define (randomly initialize) a filter matrix. Images are convolved with the filter $Z1 = X * f$

Step 3: Apply the Sigmoid activation function on the result

$$A = \text{sigmoid}(Z1)$$

Step 4: Define (randomly initialize) weight and bias matrix. Apply linear transformation on the values

$$Z2 = WT.A + b$$

Step 5: Apply the Sigmoid function on the data. This will be the final output

$$O = \text{sigmoid}(Z2)$$

The CNN model treats these values as parameters, which are randomly initialized and learned during the training process.

(Figure 3.1: framework of the proposed system)

3.1.3 proposed cnn model framework

CNN is a type of Neural Network Model which allows us to extract higher representations of an image content. Unlike the classical image recognition where images features are being defined manually, CNN takes the image's raw pixel data, trains the model, then extracts the features automatically for better classification, the proposed system CNN model is as shown in Figure 1

3.2 DATAFLOW DIAGRAM OF THE EXISTING SYSTEM

A dataflow diagram (DFD) is a way of representing a flow of data through a process or a system. The DFD also provides information about the outputs and inputs of each entity and the process itself. The Yourdon and Coad dataflow diagram of the proposed system is depicted in Figure 2.

(Figure 2.1: A Dataflow Diagram of the Proposed System)

3.2.1 System flowchart

The program flowchart depicts the step-by-step sequence of instructions, workflow or process, showing the steps as boxes of various kinds, and their order by connecting them with arrows. The diagrammatic representation illustrates a solution model to the existing system indicating the start operation and series of activities that occurred before the termination of the system processes by the stop operation as shown in Figure 3.

(Figure 3.1: A Program Flowchart of the Proposed System)

3.3 HIGH LEVEL MODEL OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

A data model is a conceptual representation of the data structures that are required by a database. The data structures include the data objects, the associations between data objects, and the rules which govern operations on the objects. As the name implies, the data model focuses on what data is required and how it should be organized rather than what operations will be performed on the data. To use a common analogy, the data model is equivalent to an architect's building plans. Hence the data model is the database structural plan of a system. Figure 4 is the high-level model of the proposed system.

(Figure 3.2: High Level Modeling of the Proposed System)

3.4 USE CASE DIAGRAM

A use case diagram is a type of UML diagram that is used to graphically depict the interactions among elements of a system. With a use case diagram, the individual roles of a system are assigned use cases to show operations they can perform. In the proposed system, there is one (1) user role which is most times referred to as an actor. This actor is the user that will make use of the system. Figure 5 shows the use case diagram of the system.

(Figure 3.4: Use Case Diagram of the Proposed System)

3.5 DATA PROCESSING TASK

Automated malaria diagnosis systems usually start with preprocessing functions such as foreign objects removal from the images. These cleaning tasks often result in improved performance of the algorithms. I did not conduct such preprocessing tasks because most of the images were prepared from cultured parasites. As such, the images do not contain white blood cells, platelets or chemical substance as is often the case for images taken in clinical settings. Also, the methods employed in this thesis work with only local regions of the images. Thus, the presence of stains or debris at other regions of the images do not affect the performance of the algorithm. Beyond basic data cleaning, however, advanced data processing functions were applied to the images. The techniques employed included parasite annotations for the growth-cycle classification task and gray-scaling for the binary classification task.

3.5.1 image annotation

A typical image in the dataset could contain more than one growth-cycle stage of the parasite. For those images, assigning a label to them is ambiguous; it could take the label of any of the growth-cycle stages present in it. Instead of assigning labels to the image, labels were assigned to sections of the image. In particular, square bounding boxes were drawn around parasites. Each bounding box was then assigned the ground truth label of the growth-cycle stage in that region. Negative patches were taken from random regions of the images not intersecting any bounding box. The annotations were performed by a malaria research expert using a tool called DragonFly. The tool was generously provided by a researcher at the University of Missouri. Trophozoites were annotated with blue bounding boxes and gametocytes were annotated with brown bounding boxes. Figure 3.2 shows examples of the annotations.

A total of 1068 annotations were generated from 353 images. The other 50 images for the growth-cycle stage classification were completely negative (did not contain any parasite). Of the 1068 annotations, 614 were for trophozoites. There were 454 annotations for gametocytes. Table 3.2 shows the distribution of the annotations for the various classes.

Table 3.2: Number of annotations for growth-cycle stage classification

Annotations	No. _ Annotations	Percentage of Total Annotations (%)
-------------	-------------------	-------------------------------------

Trophozoites	614	57.491
Gametocytes	454	42.509

3.5.1.1.1 A crop with only one tropho- (b) A crop with only one ga- (c) Multiple trophozoites in one
zoit metocyt image

(d) Multiple gametocytes in one (e) Multiple gametocytes and (f) Trophozoites and
image trophozoites in one schizonts image

Note: All annotations are treated independently.

Figure 3.2: Crops of parasites growth-cycle stage annotations

3.5.2 grayscaling

Two separate experiments were conducted for the binary classification task, one using the red green blue (RGB) images and the other using grayscale images. This was necessary because the background color of the negative samples was utterly different from the background color of the positive samples. It therefore became trivial for the algorithm to discriminate between the two classes using the color and other global statistics. This meant that the algorithm was not learning any representation peculiar to Plasmodium parasites. Gray-scaling was therefore introduced to reduce the influence of the color difference on the classification. However, as discussed in Chapter 5, both methods attained similar performance. This section describes the method which was used in the conversion from RGB to grayscale.

Choosing an RGB-to-grayscale conversion method is not trivial because the conversion method can impact the performance of the classification algorithm (Kanan and Cottrell, 2012). Some researchers adopt the Hue Saturation Value (HSV) color-to-grayscale conversion method (Bibin et al., 2017; Penas, Rivera, & Naval.Jr, 2017) while others employ a variant of the HSV method called the HSI method (Pinkaw et al., 2015). A third cate- gory of researchers

combine the two methods above as different features in the conversion process (Purnama et al., 2013).

In the HSV method, the maximum value of the RGB channels is used as the grayscale value. That is, $Y_{HSV} = \max(R, G, B)$. This preserves the maximum brightness of the image in question. Unfortunately, preserving the maximum brightness makes HSV vulnerable to changes in the image brightness (Kanan and Cottrell, 2012). This renders HSV an unsuitable RGB-to-grayscale conversion method for problems where the images vary. The brightness problem induced by HSV is resolved by averaging the gamma corrected R, G, B values. That is,

Y_{Gleam}

(R^J, G^J, B^J) where R^J, G^J, B^J are the gamma corrected values. This method is the best RGB-to-grayscale conversion method for most classification tasks (Kanan and Cottrell, 2012). They used gleam for RGB-to-grayscale conversion because of the advantages it has over HSV and the other conversion methods. An implementation of Gleam was retrieved from OpenCV which used Equation 1 in the implementation.

$$Y \leftarrow 0.229.R + 0.587.G + 0.114.B \quad (1)$$

Figure 3.3 shows an example of an image and its grayscale version

(Figure 3.3: RGB and grayscale images)

3.6.2.1 RGB Image. As shown in the 3.6.2.2 Grayscale version of (a). picture, the background color of the Although the grayscale form has less RGB is so conspicuous that it can background color, it preserves the affect the classifier's performance. structure of the parasites which is the important feature for classification Unlike most studies in malaria diagnosis, no hand-engineered features were supplied to the convolutional neural networks.

However, a lot of techniques including data augmentation, transfer learning and context encoding have been employed to prevent the model from over-fitting the data. These techniques are discussed in succeeding sections.

3.5.3 Data augmentation

CNNs often require big datasets in order to obtain good performance on new unseen examples. Data augmentation is often used to increase the training datasets in cases where the number of training examples is small (Penas et al., 2017). In data augmentation, new samples are generated artificially using mostly transformation functions. Besides increasing the size of the training set, data augmentation is used to balance the number of examples for each class in the training set (Quinn et al., 2016). This is achieved by exerting a weighted augmentation to each of the classes. Classes with large representations in the dataset are augmented less compared to classes with small number of examples in the training set. Balancing the training set usually improves the performance of the model.

Three artificial examples were generated for each of 1068 annotations as reported in the subsection 3.2.1 above. Augmentation was achieved through the three methods below.

- Horizontal flip: the new image is an instance of the original image reflected along its horizontal axis.
- Vertical flip: the new image is an instance of the original image reflected along its vertical axis.
- Rotation through 90°: the new image is an instance of the original image rotated 90° clockwise.

3.6 DEALING WITH LITTLE LABELED DATA

The main challenge with using CNNs is that they require large datasets. This project did not have such a large dataset required by the model. The issues posed by the small dataset were addressed through transfer learning and unsupervised pre-training. These methods were used to generate good initialization weights for the classification tasks. This section discusses these two techniques.

3.6.1 Transfer learning

In many applications related to medical imaging, it is often impractical to obtain large labeled datasets sufficient to train a CNN from scratch (Afridi, Ross, and Shapiro, 2018). Transfer learning is often used to address the problem of limited labeled data. Transfer learning is passing on the knowledge contained in a model pre-trained on a larger dataset to the problem with limited data. Transfer learning has been used in many

computer vision malaria research studies resulting in improved performance (Sivaramakrishnan, Antani, and Jaeger, 2017; Penas et al., 2017). In the context of CNNs, transfer learning is often used for fine-tuning. This is the transplantation of the learned feature layers of a CNN trained on a large dataset to initialize the CNN for the smaller dataset. Classes with large representations in the dataset are augmented less compared to classes with small number of examples in the training set. Balancing the training set usually improves the performance of the model.

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In order to obtain optimum performance using transfer learning, the source dataset and the target dataset must have similar characteristics (Sivaramakrishnan et al., 2017; Yosinski, Clune, Bengio, & Lipson, 2014).

However, other studies suggest that transfer learning can still yield improvement in performance even when the source task is specifically different from the target tasks

(Afridi et al., 2018). This means that if there are no pre-trained models in the target problem’s domain, a more general pretrained model can still be fine-tuned with the unrelated data.

Although more images were created through data augmentation, the total number of samples was not still sufficient to train a CNN from scratch to obtain good performance. Transfer learning was used to supplement the data augmentation to prevent over-fitting. Ideally, the source CNN should have been pre-trained on Giemsa-stained images if not on images of Plasmodium parasites. Unfortunately, such pre-trained models are currently not available. The reason is that generally, Giemsa-stained images datasets are always small to begin with. Since no ideal pre-trained model could be found, the VGG16 network (Simonyan & Zisserman, 2014) pre-trained on ImageNet (Russakovsky et al., 2015) was used as the source model.

Only the convolutional blocks of the VGG16 network were downloaded. However, only the last three layers were trainable. The activations from the last convolutional layer was fed to a custom-made fully connected layer before the output layer. The diagram below shows the architecture of the pre-trained model. The VGG16 network was chosen for its simplicity and speed. The focus of the experiment, however, was not on the details of the specific network used. The architecture of the fine-tuned model is shown in Figure 3.4.

(Figure 3.4: Fine-tuned VGG16 architecture)

3.7.2 Context encoding

Besides data-augmentation and transfer learning, context encoding has typically been used to address the challenges introduced by the lack of large labeled data. Context encoding is the process of training a CNN to generate the contents of an image region based on its surroundings (Pathak et al., 2016). The context encoder can then be used as an initialization to other tasks where there is not enough data.

A context encoder typically has two components: an encoder network and a decoder model. The encoder learns the properties of the input image based on the context. The decoder reconstructs the original image from the output of the encoder. This project used the context encoder used in (Pathak et al., 2016). Pathak et al. used AlexNet up to layer 5 for the encoder. The decoder was implemented through rescaling and up-sampling. Unlike Pathak et al., this project used only the L2 reconstruction loss in training the context encoder. The implementation of the adversarial discriminator as in

Pathank et al. was not considered because of the large training time required for the adversarial loss.

Two-thousand seven hundred and three (2,703) Giemsa-stained thick bloodsmears were used to train the context encoder. Arbitrarily selected region of each image was in-painted (destroyed). That region of the image in addition to 35 pixels wide context around it was feed to the encoder. The decoder was task to reproduce the contents of the images which were destroyed. Examples of the inpainted images and the corresponding ground-truth images are shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Random crops and their inpaintings for unsupervised pre-training

3.8 SEMANTIC SEGMENTATION

This subsection discusses the processes which were used to conduct the growthcycle stages classification. Each Giemsa-stained thin blood smear typically contains Plasmodium parasites at different growth-cycles and normal RBCs. Therefore, different regions of a given image should contain different labels in order to detect different growth-cycle stages. Regions of the images containing parasites were identified through annotations as discussed in subsection 3.2.1.

Given the annotations, one way to perform the growth-cycle stages classification is to treat each annotation as an independent image (Quinn et al., 2016). In that approach, negative samples are created by taking random crops of the images not covered by any annotation. This approach, known as the sliding-window approach poses several challenges. The first challenge is that the annotations must have the same spatial dimensions. Secondly, passing windows of the image through the network individually is computationally expensive. Finally, the sliding-window approach is slow at test time since all patches(windows) of the test image must be evaluated. These deficiencies render the sliding-window

technique ineffective.

Instead of creating labeled patches of the images, each pixel in the image can be assigned a label. This approach is called semantic segmentation. Semantic segmentation is a pixel-wise classification. Each pixel in the input image is classified into one of K possible classes. Although semantic segmentation requires many predictions, it is computationally efficient because all pixels in an image are passed through the network together. Different CNN based semantic segmentation techniques have been proposed in the literature (Gupta, Girshick, and Arbel, 2014; Cires and Giusti, 2012) but that of only Long, Shelhamer and Darrell (2015) is discussed here.

Long et al. were the first to propose a fully convolutional neural networks (FCNs) for semantic segmentation. Essentially, they replaced the fully connected layers typically at the end of CNNs with convolutional layers. The low-resolution outputs of the convolutional layers are up sampled to the input resolutions for pixel wise predictions. FCNs have since emerged as the method of choice for semantic segmentation tasks due to their ability to achieve good performances on image segmentation. It is those same successes which motivated the use of FCNs in this research. The implementation involved adding convolutional layers to a pre-trained VGG16 model as discussed in subsection 3.4.1 to provide initialize parameters. Upsampling was achieved through transpose convolutions (Wojna et al., 2017). Advanced methods such as skip connections were not included in the implementation. The architecture of the semantic segmentation network used for growth-cycle stage classification is shown in Figure 3.6.

(Figure 3.6: Growth-cycle stages classification model architecture)

The inputs of the Input Layer are the raw images and their labels. FCL=Fully Convolutional Layer, Con Layer = Convolutional Layer. Each succeeding layer takes input from the previous layer.

3.8.1 masks generation

In order to perform semantic segmentation, each pixel in the images had to be labeled into one

of three classes: negative (normal cell), trophozoites and gametocytes. These labels for each image are known as the mask of the image. Each mask contained the same number of pixels as the original images. However, unlike the original images which had three values for each pixel, the masks had only one value for each pixel. Furthermore, each mask had only three distinct values (0, 1, 2) indicating the labels of the pixels. That is, a 1 at index (x, y) in a mask indicates that the pixel at index (x, y) in the corresponding ground-truth image belongs to a trophozoite. Normal cells were labeled with 0 and 2 represented gametocytes.

The masks were generated using the ground truth annotations of the images some of which are shown in Figure 3.2. Each annotation in an image was associated with four distinct coordinates representing the different vertices of that annotation and a label indicating the growth-cycle stage of the parasite. The structure of an annotation was of the form: filename-annotation index, label, comment, geometric shape, x1, y1, x2, y2, x3, y3, x4, y4, x1, y1. Thus, each pixel can be labeled using the label of the annotation and the pixel positions given by the coordinates.

In the ground-truth annotations, some of the annotations were not axis-aligned as the example in Figure 3.2. This posed challenges when assigning the labels because it required slicing matrices diagonally which is difficult. As a result, all annotations were rotated to align with the axes of the images. In order to rotate an annotation, a tight bounding box was drawn around the annotation such that the bounding box covered the area previously occupied by the annotation. That is, the area of an annotation is a lower bound on the area of the bounding box for that annotation. This ensured that no regions of the actual parasites were lost to rotation. In consequence, more normal cells were labeled as either belonging to trophozoites or gametocytes. The detail algorithm of how the bounding boxes were generated is not covered here. The results of the rotations, however, is shown in Figure

3.7. The coordinates of the bounding boxes together with the corresponding labels were then used to label all the pixels.

Figure 3.7: A non-aligned annotation and its rotated equivalent

3.8.2 downsampling

In CNNs, large mini-batch sizes enable the computation of good gradients which improves learning (Radiuk, 2018). The size of mini-batches are limited by the resolution of the images and the amount of available memory capacity. The higher the resolution of the images, the more memory they require to train the models. Semantic segmentation models require a lot of memory to train because the labels (masks) are also large. (The masks have the same dimensionality as the ground-truth images). This makes training high resolution images very expensive. As a result, high resolution images are usually downsampled to lower resolution expensive. As a lower to the amount of memory consumption. The amount of down-sampling usually depend on the problem domain and the original resolution of the images. That said, the downsampled images should remain meaningful to the problem. Thus, the downsampled images should maintain the characteristics of the original images which are relevant to the classification task.

The images for the growth-cycle stage classification had original resolutions of $1500 \times 2100 \times 3$. At this resolution, the model could be trained on a mini-batch of only two images on a 15GB Graphical Processing Unit (GPU). In order to train at much larger mini-batches, the images were down sampled to $764 \times 1055 \times 3$ resolution. Consequently, the masks generated at the higher resolutions (1500×2110) were also downsampled to 764×1055 pixels. Both the images and the masks were down sampled using inverse mapping. With regards to the interpolation methods, bi-linear interpolation was used for the images. The masks were down sampled using nearest-neighbor interpolation.

In bi-linear interpolation, the value of a pixel in the down sampled image is a weighted average of the values of all pixels in the original image which map to that pixel. This makes the low-resolution images look visually similar to the high-resolution images. In nearest-neighbor interpolation, a pixel in the low resolution image is assigned the intensity of the pixel closest to it in the high resolution image determined by some algorithm. Nearest-neighbor is particularly good for down sampling the masks because it preserves the integer labels. Illustrations of these down sampling methods are shown in Figure 3.8. The masks at the original masks and down sampled masks are also shown in Figure 3.9.

3.9.2.1 Bi-linear interpolation. The output intensity is an average of the surrounding intensities.

3.9.2.2 Nearest-neighbor interpolation. The output intensity is the intensity of the closest pixel determine by some algorithm

Figure 3.8: Illustrations of downsampling methods

3.9.2.2.1 Ground-truth annotations

3.9.2.2.2 Masks at original resolution - Unlike the ground-truth annotations, the masks are up-right bounding boxes. Nonetheless, the relative sizes and positions of annotations are preserved. In the masks, all regions of the image not annotated are labeled as negative (gray)

3.9.2.2.3 Masks at down sampled resolution - Although the down sampled images are smaller than the original images in terms of size, the relative ordering of the masks are maintained.

3.8.3 Weighting of the loss function

As noted in the Methodology, all the models use categorical cross entropy as the loss function. In its pure form, categorical cross entropy treats predictions on all the classes equally. As a result, it penalizes all wrong predictions with the same magnitude. This feature of the loss function is undesirable when the training set is unbalanced. This is because when using an unbalanced training dataset with a level-plain loss function, the model will always try to predict the class with the largest proportion. The reason is that by always predicting that class, the model is assured of making correct predictions most of the time. For instance, if the training set comprises of 1000 examples belong to class A and 10 examples belonging to class B, the model is guaranteed ≈ 99 percent accuracy by always predicting class A.

The training dataset for the semantic segmentation model is extremely unbalanced as shown in Table 4.2. This means that using categorical cross-entropy as discussed in the Methodology will induce the model to always classify every pixel as belonging to the negative class. This is undesirable because the model will never learn the characteristics of trophozoites and gametocytes which distinguish them from each other and from normal cells. However, if the model is made to pay an extra penalty for making wrong predictions on the least represented classes, it will be encouraged to learn the properties of the different classes. Conversely, correct predictions on the least represented classes lead to a low total loss value. The weighted loss function expressed in Equation 15 was used to resolve the problem of trivial predictions due to the unbalanced training set.

$$H = \frac{\sum N}{Y^c + \epsilon^{y^c}} H$$

where

H = overall weighted loss (15)

N = A normalization constant. N is set to the total number of pixels $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$,
 A small positive constant to prevent division by zero

Y^c = The number of pixels in ground-truth labels belonging to class c

H_{y^c} = The categorical cross entropy loss of the predictions on class c

Using the above formula, predictions on the negative class are treated with less importance because the denominator is large. Conversely, the predictions on gametocytes is treated with high importance because the loss contributed by wrong predictions on gametocytes is penalized heavily.

To verify that a weighted loss function was actually required, the model was trained using an unweighted categorical cross-entropy. As expected, the model predicted every pixel as negative as shown in Figure 3.10.

(Figure 3.10: Activation map from unweighted loss)

3.9.2.3 Ground-truth label of an image the model had not seen before. Tasked with producing this image, it produced the image in (b) because the number of pixels labeled as negative outnumber the other categories

CHAPTER FOUR: SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The application had two major components:

- a training module and
- testing module.

As should be expected, the application behaves differently for the two components. A flow chart diagram of the application is shown in Figure 4.1 below.

Figure 4.1: System flowchart

4.2 IMPLEMENTATION RESOURCES

The model was developed using three main packages in python:

- OpenCV,
- Keras and
- TensorFlow.

These packages provide highly optimized implementations of the machinelearning algorithms which used in this project. Adopting these packages reduced the amountof boiler-plate code required for testing the algorithms. Also, since many researchers use those libraries,

adopting them makes it easier for other people to verify the results.

4.2.1 OpenCV

OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision Library) is a BSD-licensed open-source computer vision and machine learning library. OpenCV was mainly used for image preprocessing tasks such as conversion from RGB images to grayscale, image down sampling and descaling. Since OpenCV was built to take advantage of multi-core processor systems, the functions are highly optimized for matrix operations. OpenCV thus offered faster implementations of the image processing tasks used in this implementation.

4.2.2 Keras

"Keras is a high-level neural networks API, written in Python and capable of running on top of TensorFlow, CNTK, or Theano. It was developed with a focus on enabling fast experimentation" (Keras, 2018). The extract above, taken from Keras documentation, summarizes the main reasons why Keras has emerged as the default library for computer vision research. Keras works on both GPU and CPU, has many different optimization and loss functions, and provides mechanisms for saving the model at various checkpoints. The context encoder and the main classification models were developed using the Keras API. Keras also provided the pre-trained model as well as the data augmentation functions used in this research.

TensorFlow was the back-end library for Keras. Although no code was written directly in TensorFlow, all the Keras computations were executed in TensorFlow. Thus, the next subsection discusses the motivation why TensorFlow was chosen as the back-end library.

4.2.3 TensorFlow

TensorFlow is a machine learning software library that was developed by Google Brain Team for research in Google. Since becoming an open-sourced library in 2015 under Apache License 2.0., many researchers and software companies have adopted TensorFlow for their intelligence research. TensorFlow uses data flow graphs for all its computations. Mathematical operations are represented as nodes while data is represented as edges(tensors) which designed to handle multidimensional data. This makes TensorFlow well suited for image processing applications since images are generally processed in their spatial form. Finally, TensorFlow provides seamless transition between CPU and GPU, which Keras ex-

plots to speed up training.

4.3 Training

All the models were trained using the Google Compute Engine Application Programming Interface (API). This became necessary because the models could not be trained fast enough on CPUs because they contained many parameters. One of the models experimented for the semantic segmentation task for instance had 31,095,763 trainable parameters. It takes a long time to train such models on CPUs since CPUs often execute instructions sequentially. An interesting observation, however, is that most of the operations in CNNs are computations on matrices. Since matrix operations are mostly element-wise operations, they can be executed in parallel. Graphical Processing Units(GPUs), designed for processing spatial data have the ability to execute many instructions in parallel. Hence, training on a GPU can reduce training time from days to hours.

For comparison purposes, the binary classification model was experimented on both the GPU and on an i-3 Intel CPU with a 4GB RAM. For twenty epochs, it took the GPU only six(6) minutes to finish training the model while it took the CPU almost three days to train the model. Additionally, the CPU could train on only a mini-batch size of 1 whilst the GPU trained on a mini-batch of 42 images. Besides the number of parameters, the input features had very high resolution (764 by 1055 by 3). The high dimensionality of the data combined with the large number of parameters meant that training the models required large Random Access Memory(RAM). Personal computers, being largely general purpose machines, are not equipped with powerful GPUs and often have relatively smaller RAM compared to that which the models needed. Fortunately, the computational power required for training CNNs is accessible through Google Cloud's API. All the models experimented in this research were trained on a virtual machine⁶ provided through the Compute Engine API. The virtual machine was equipped with a NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPU running on Compute Unified Device Architecture(CUDA) Toolkit 9.0 from NVIDIA.

The details of the virtual machine's GPU are shown in Figure 4.2.

```

NVIDIA-SMI 390.30              Driver Version: 390.30
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
GPU  Name                Persistence-M| Bus-Id        Disp.A | Volatile Uncorr. ECC
Fan  Temp  Perf  Pwr:Usage/Cap|      Memory-Usage | GPU-Util  Compute M.
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
 0   Tesla P100-PCIE...  Off          | 00000000:00:04.0 Off  |      0%      0
N/A  41C    P0     28W / 250W | 82MiB / 16280MiB |          Default
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
Processes:
GPU  PID  Type  Process name          GPU Memory
-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
 0   1854  G    /usr/lib/xorg/Xorg    82MiB

```

The GPU has a total of 16GB internal memory and a compute capability of 6

Figure 4.2: GPU properties

4.3.1 Binary Classification

The binary classification model was trained on 323 images and validated on 168 images. In order to avoid loading all the images into memory at once, the model was implemented to read the data from disk on demand. Data augmentation techniques were applied to both the training and validation datasets. That is, new images belonging to the two datasets were generated infinitely for training the model and evaluating the model. The binary classification model used a VGG16 pre-trained model for parameter initialization. All the layers of the pre-trained model except the last three were frozen. That is, only the last three layers were fine-tuned. The pre-trained model was extended by stacking two fully connected layers and an output layer on top of it. The model was regularized using one dropout layer immediately before the output layer. The model had a total of 22,087,682 parameters with only 12,092,610 of them being trainable. The input resolution was $500 \times 500 \times 3$ pixels.

The model was trained for 100 epochs using a learning rate of 10^{-5} . The data was supplied in mini-batches of 32 images for training and 10 images for validation making a combined total of 42 images per mini-batch. The GPU took ≈ 18 seconds for each epoch. Thus, it took 30 minutes to train the model.

4.3.2 Growth-cycle Stages Classification

The growth-cycle stage classification problem was modeled as a semantic segmentation problem as discussed in the Methodology above. The model was initialized using unsupervised pre-training and transfer learning to compensate for the little dataset. This section discusses how the model was trained. First, however, is an overview of the dataset which was used to train the model.

Three hundred and fifty-three (353) images in total contained at least one parasite. Ninety percent of the 353 images representing 318 images were used to train and validate the model. The other 10% of the dataset was reserved for testing the model at the end of training. The model was evaluated once on the test data. The details of the training and test datasets in terms of annotations and in terms of pixel counts are provided in Table 4.1 and in Table 4.2 respectively. The reported number of pixels are for the low-resolution images which were used for training. The number of pixels between the true parasites were approximately equally distributed as shown through the percentage representations in Table 4.3.

Besides dividing the data into training and test datasets, a subsection of the training dataset was used for validation. Validation is the testing of the model on some data which is not used in computing the gradients. Although, 63 images representing 20% of the training data were used for validation, the composition of the validation set changed across different training jobs. That is, in each training job, the parameters were updated on the gradients of only 255 original images selected randomly from 318 images; with the other 63 images preserved for validation. In addition to these ground-truth images, both the training and validation sets were artificially boosted through data augmentation.

Table 4.1: Composition of annotations in Training and Test datasets

Dataset	Total No. _ Images	No. _ Trophozoites	No. _ Gametocytes	Total Annotations
Training Data	318	571(58.44%)	406(41.56%)	977
Test Data	35	43(47.25%)	48(52.75%)	91

Table 4.2: Number of pixels per class in Training and Test datasets

Dataset	Total No. _ of Pixels	Negative Pixels	Trophozoites Pixels	Gametocytes Pixels
Training Data	256, 314, 360	249, 747, 634	2, 874, 959	3, 598, 047
Test Data	28, 210,700	27, 462, 705	245, 912	492, 827

Table 4.3: Number of pixels per class in percentages

Dataset	Total No. _ of Pixels	Negative (%)	Trophozoites(%)	Gametocytes(%)
Training Data	256, 314, 360	97.43	1.12	1.45
Test Data	28, 210,700	97.35	0.90	1.75

4.3.3 Training the model

Several models were experimented in this research. However, this section discusses only the model which was eventually used on the test data. That model was trained for 200 epochs using an adaptive learning rate with $\alpha_0 = 10^{-4}$ on a GPU. The GPU could only load up to 19 images due to memory constraints. As a result, 17 images were used for training and two images for validation in each training epoch. The number of training steps and validation steps were computed by dividing the size of dataset with the mini-batch sizes. This resulted in 25 training steps and 31 validation steps. It took the GPU ≈ 53 seconds on average to execute each epoch. Thus, it took 2 hours 57 minutes to train the model completely⁸.

4.4 Results of Training

The main concern during training was how the trained model would fair on unseen data. This meant that choices about hyper-parameters values, model size and degree of regularization were based largely on the validation accuracy and validation loss. The training accuracy and training loss were also monitored in addition to the validation metrics.

4.4.1 Binary Classification Results

After the 20th training epoch, the model seemed to have reached an optimal point as the training accuracy reached 99.70 percent and the validation accuracy reached 98.78 percent. In addition, the validation loss and training losses both decayed toward zero as the plot of the loss in 5.2a show. This meant that the model was not over-fitting the data. This profound ease of discriminating between the two classes after only 20 iterations was baffling. It turned out, however, that in principle the model was not discriminating between the two classes based on the presence or absence of *Plasmodium* parasites. It used trivial properties of the images such as differences in contexts to classify them. From the plot of samples belonging to the two classes shown in Figure 5.1, it is evident that the images could indeed be classified trivially. Methods such as grayscaling were applied to the images to reduce the contextual differences between the two classes. However, all of them proved futile in producing images which could force the model to learn the characteristics of the *Plasmodium* parasites. Advance techniques such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) (Goodfellow et al., 2014) could have produced better performance but there was little time to explore such techniques. Plots of the training and validation metrics of the model are shown in Figure 4.2.

4.4.1 Positive image

(b) Negative image

(c) Another positive image - The positive images are a mixture of Giemsa-thin and thick blood smears of *Plasmodium* parasites. However, they are unlike the negative images.

(d)

Another negative image - The negative images do not look like anything produced from stained blood smears. Even within the negative images, they are large variations with regards to background and generate semantic properties. This apparent difference between positive and negative images makes the classification extremely easy for the network.

(Figure 4.1: Examples of positive and negative images from binary classification dataset)

Diagram for Training and validation losses

Diagram for Training and validation accuracies

(Figure 5.2: Binary classification training metrics)

4.4.2 Growth-cycle Stage Classification Results

The growth-cycle stage classification model achieved final training and validation accuracies of 91.25 percent after several training iterations. The model exhibited several characteristics which made training difficult. The first generation of the model had 4,962,051 trainable parameters. Training at a learning rate of 10^{-5} , the training and validation metrics showed that the model was too simple to properly describe the data as shown in the plots in Figure 5.3. This triggered a revision of the model's architecture to 31,095,763 parameters in an attempt to address the observed under-fitting. The revision process included fine-tuning the last three layers of the pre-trained model and convolving to a resolution of 17×26 pixels before upsampling. The learning rate was also increased to 10^{-4} . Unfortunately, the model became too powerful that it exhibited strong over-fitting as shown in Figure 5.4. It was evident the model was over-fitting the data because both the training and validation unweighted accuracies kept increasing steadily towards 100 percent. However, unlike the weighted training loss which kept decreasing, the weighted validation loss increased as training progressed. This meant that the model became worse and worse at classifying unseen samples. To verify that the trend was indeed increasing continuously, the number of training epochs was increased to 250. This resulted in the plots shown in Figure 4.5. At about the 250th epoch, both the training and validation unweighted accuracies reached 91 but the validation loss skyrocketed too, a confirmation that the model was over-fitting. Despite the observed over-fitting, this model was kept for evaluation at test time whilst revisions were made for better architectures. This model was labeled as model A.

To prevent the unconventional scenarios where both validation loss and accuracy moved in the same direction, the accuracies were also weighted to be on the same scale as

the loss. The accuracies where weighted using the formula

$$\text{Accweighted} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \sum_c \mathbb{1}_{y_i = \hat{y}_i \wedge y_i = c} \} \underline{Y_c}$$

Where (16)

- K = The number of classes
- Y_c = The number of pixels belonging to class c
- N = The total number of pixels in the mini-batch

Using Eqn 16 as the new accuracy metric, adaptive learning rate, advanced regularization and more architecture search, the model was reconstructed to 5,122,307 parameters. The reconstructed model showed evidence of tangible learning after 200 training epochs. This can be seen in the plots shown in Figure 5.6. Additionally, plots of the activation maps of the model on unseen data as displayed in Figure 5.8 indicated strong learning. This became model B. Motivated by the promise of these observations, a similar model, model C, was developed with 6,761,091 learnable parameters through the addition of two fully convolutional layers and changes in the number of filters. Using the same hyper-parameters as the previous model, the new model converged to a local minimum after 130 epochs as shown in Figure 5.7. The test data was then evaluated independently on these three models. It turned out the over-fitting model whose training statistics are shown in Figure 5.5 performed better than the other two models on the test images.

4.5 RESULTS FOR TESTING

4.5.1 Binary Classification Test Results

Hundred images from the growth-cycle stage classification dataset were used to evaluate the binary classification model. Fifty percent of the test data were positive images while the other 50 percent contained no parasites. Using the images from growth-cycle data to evaluate the binary classification model was motivated by the following main reasons:

- There was a need to evaluate the model on a test set with similar global statistics between the two classes. This eliminated the influence of background and context in the evaluation of the model. Since both datasets were Giemsa-thin blood smear images, the model was expected to produce accurate results if it indeed learned the characteristics of *Plasmodium* parasites when trained on the dataset for binary classification. On the other hand, if it learned only the global statistics, it was expected to classify every image from the growth-cycle dataset as positive. The dataset for the growth-cycle stage classification task had the desired properties, hence the decision to use some of those images for testing.

- There was no independent dataset for testing the binary classification model.

As anticipated, the model classified all the 100 images as positive although 50% of the images were negative. To ensure that the model's poor performance was not due to errors in the evaluation process, 100 images from the binary classification training dataset (50 positive and 50 negative images) were also used to evaluate the model. This time round, the model classified all the images perfectly into the two classes. This confirmed that the model's training performance was indeed based on global statistics of the images. The GPU took ≈ 54 seconds to evaluate the 100 images.

4.5.2 Grow-cycle Stages Classification Test Results

The growth-cycle stages classification model was tested on 35 images none of which the model had seen prior to testing. Like the training dataset, the masks were constructed for the test images using their annotations. However, unlike the masks of the training data, the masks of the test data were generated purposely for measuring the accuracy of the predictions and not for gradient computations. The three most promising models labeled A, B, and C as discussed above were evaluated independently on the test data. The best model, model A, was able to predict the class of every pixel in the 35 images with a weighted accuracy of 85.86%. Model B obtained a weighted accuracy of 51.19% while Model C achieved an accuracy of 44.63%. The architecture of best model, model A is shown in Figure 3.6. Given that semantic segmentation is generally a difficult task, it can be concluded that the results though relatively low compared to many categorizations tasks, were modest given the size of the dataset. More importantly, the model achieved similar performance on both training and testing. This indicates that it will perform well when applied to other Giemsa- stained thin blood smears.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 SUMMARY

This research explored the application of convolutional neural networks in the detection of *Plasmodium* parasites. In particular, a semantic segmentation model was built to classify the different growth-cycle stages of *Plasmodium* parasites. Through the use of techniques such as transfer learning and regularization methods, the model classified pixels belonging to normal cells, trophozoites or gametocytes with a weighted accuracy of 85.86 percent. A binary classification model was also built to classify Giemsa-stained thin blood smear images into positive and negative classes. That model achieved an accuracy of 98.78 percent during training but performed poorly at test time because of large variations in the training data.

These empirical results from the experiments on the dense predictions are consistent with the literature that convolutional neural networks can be used to automate microscopy especially for the case of malaria diagnosis. In an attempt to classify the different growth-cycle stages, this research became the first of its kind (to the best of my knowledge) to perform dense predictions on Giemsa-stained thin blood images. This provides a good foundation for complete segmentations of *Plasmodium* parasites from stained images. Also, the ability to identify different growth-cycle stages of *Plasmodium* parasites at the pixel level can help reveal some properties of the parasites which cannot be accessed otherwise.

5.2 LIMITATIONS

This section discusses the aspects of the research which had the potential to adversely affect the accuracy of the classification algorithms. The following were constraints on the performance of the models.

- The VGG16 pre-trained model which was used to initialize the models was not in the problem domain. As stated in the Methodology, the VGG16 model was pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset which does not contain medical image data. The ImageNet pre-trained model was used because no pre-trained model in malaria diagnosis was found. Since transfer learning works well when the source model and the target model

are in the same domain, applying a model trained on cats and dogs to a model on *Plasmodium* parasites could have impacted the performance of the model negatively. To reduce the impact of the differences in the problem domain, the last three layers of the VGG16 model were re-trained. In addition, a fully convolutional layer was put on top of the the pre-trained model before upsampling. Since the first layers of CNNs typically learn general features such as curves, fine-tuning only the last layers improved the model's performance.

- The dataset employed in the study was very small. It is a well established fact that CNNs perform very well when they are trained on large datasets. In fact, the recent successes of deep learning have been attribute mainly to advancements in archiving massive datasets (Brynjolfsson and Andrew, 2017). CNNs normally tend to over-fit small datasets which subsequently leads to poor performance at test time. As dis- cussed above, several methods were employed to prevent over-fitting but they do not rule out the fact that the project could have benefited from more data.
- Some of the parasite annotations were ill-constructed. The images were annotated using square bounding boxes because they required less time to construct. In using square bounding boxes, however, the annotations deviated from the true morphologies of the parasites. A gametocyte being crescent in shape cannot be segmented exactly with a square bounding box. Furthermore, there were slight variations in the mount of background the annotations added to infected cells. Finally, some annotations werenot axis-aligned and had to be rotated. The rotations had the potential of increasing the area of the infected cells. This meant that some normal pixels could be wrongly labeled as belonging to one of the two growth-cycle stages. To address these problems, the model was built to a very low resolution of 17×26 pixels before upsampling. Nonetheless, some of the bounding boxes still had the potential to misrepresent the true content of the images.
- The final limitation of the study is that the images had large resolutions. At the origi- nal resolution, only two images could be supplied to the model in a mini-batch. Both

the images and the masks were subsequently downsampled by a factor of two in order to feed the model with more images in a mini-batch. (At the downsampled resolutions, 17 images could be supplied to the model in a mini-batch). Although good downsampling techniques were used, the downsampling was still a potential source of error in the performance of the model.

5.3 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

This section offers suggested extensions to this study. Besides employing measures to address the limitations above, the findings of this study can become widely applicable if the following extensions are explored.

- A refinement of the algorithm to count the number of the different growth-cycle stages of the parasites per image. This feature will make it possible to estimate the density of the parasites on the images. This information is useful to health practitioners and researchers since it enables them to estimate the severity of the infection.
- An improvement of the model to include all four major growth-cycle stages of the *Plasmodium* parasite. This study considered only trophozoites and gametocytes in addition to normal cells due to constraints on image quality. Future extensions of this project should source data good enough to discriminate between all the different-growth cycle stages. The importance of classifying all life-cycle stages cannot be overstated.

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APPENDIX I

Import Libraries

```
import os, shutil
import split_folders
import random
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import itertools
from tqdm import tqdm, tqdm_notebook
import cv2
from scipy import stats
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, roc_curve, auc, classification_report, precision_score, recall_score
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
```

```
import skimage
import skimage.segmentation
import copy
```

```
# Data Visualization
```

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline
plt.style.use('ggplot')
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.image as mpimg
```

```
import tensorflow as tf
print(tf.__version__)
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from tensorflow.keras.models import Model
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Input, Flatten, Dense, MaxPooling2D, Conv2D, Dropout
from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg19 import VGG19
from tensorflow.keras.optimizers import SGD, RMSprop, Adam
from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import ModelCheckpoint, EarlyStopping, ReduceLROnPlateau
from tensorflow.keras.applications.imagenet_utils import decode_predictions
```

Load data and split the data into training, validation and testing datasets

```
original_dataset = os.path.join('/Users/rajesharasada/Desktop/malaria','cell_images')
original_dataset_parasitized = os.path.join(original_dataset, 'Parasitized')
original_dataset_uninfected = os.path.join(original_dataset, 'Uninfected')
```

```
# Create a base dir
```

```
if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected'):
    base_dir = '/Users/rajesharasada/Desktop/malaria/healthy_and_infected'
    os.mkdir(base_dir)
```

```
# Make train, valid and test directories
```

```
#train
```

```
if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/train'):
    train_dir = os.path.join(base_dir, 'train')
    os.mkdir(train_dir)
```

```
#valid
```

```
if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/valid'):
```

```

    valid_dir = os.path.join(base_dir, 'valid')
    os.mkdir(valid_dir)
#test
if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/test'):
    test_dir = os.path.join(base_dir, 'test')
    os.mkdir(test_dir)

# Make directories for infected images in each of the train, valid and test directories
if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/train/inf'):
    infected_trn_dir = os.path.join(train_dir, 'inf')
    os.mkdir(
infected_trn_dir)

if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/valid/inf'):
    infected_valid_dir = os.path.join(valid_dir, 'inf')
    os.mkdir(
infected_valid_dir)

if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/test/inf'):
    infected_test_dir = os.path.join(test_dir, 'inf')
    os.mkdir(
infected_test_dir)

# Make directories for healthy images in each of the train, valid and test directories
if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/train/healthy'):
    healthy_trn_dir = os.path.join(train_dir, 'healthy')
    os.mkdir(
healthy_trn_dir)

if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/valid/healthy'):
    healthy_valid_dir = os.path.join(valid_dir, 'healthy')
    os.mkdir(
healthy_valid_dir)

if not os.path.isdir('healthy_and_infected/test/healthy'):
    healthy_test_dir = os.path.join(test_dir, 'healthy')
    os.mkdir(
healthy_test_dir)
# Copies the first 10981 infected images to the infected_train_dir
fnames = ['Infected_{}.png'.format(i) for i in range(1,10981)]
for fname in fnames:
    src = os.path.join(original_dataset_parasitized, fname)
    dst = os.path.join(
infected_trn_dir, fname)
    shutil.copyfile(src,dst)
# Copies the 1400 infected images (10981, 12382) to the infected_valid_dir
fnames = ['Infected_{}.png'.format(i) for i in range(10981, 12382)]
for fname in fnames:
    src = os.path.join(original_dataset_parasitized, fname)
    dst = os.path.join(
infected_valid_dir, fname)
    shutil.copyfile(src,dst)

### Copy another 1400 infected images () to the infected_test_dir
fnames = ['Infected_{}.png'.format(i) for i in range(12382,13780)]
for fname in fnames:
    src = os.path.join(original_dataset_parasitized, fname)
    dst = os.path.join(
infected_test_dir, fname)
    shutil.copyfile(src,dst)

# Copies the first 10981 infected images to the infected_train_dir
fnames = ['Uninfected_{}.png'.format(i) for i in range(1, 10981)]
for fname in fnames:
    src = os.path.join(original_dataset_uninfected, fname)

```

```

dst = os.path.join(healthy_trn_dir, fname)
shutil.copyfile(src,dst)

# Copies the 1400 infected images (10981, 12382) to the infected_valid_dir
fnames = ['Uninfected_{}.png'.format(i) for i in range(10981, 12382)]
for fname in fnames:
    src = os.path.join(original_dataset_uninfected, fname)
    dst = os.path.join(healthy_valid_dir, fname)
    shutil.copyfile(src,dst)

### Copy another 1400 infected images () to the infected_test_dir
fnames = ['Uninfected_{}.png'.format(i) for i in range(12382,13780)]
for fname in fnames:
    src = os.path.join(original_dataset_uninfected, fname)
    dst = os.path.join(healthy_test_dir, fname)
    shutil.copyfile(src,dst)

print("{} Infected training images:".format(len(os.listdir(infected_trn_dir))))
print("{} Uninfected training images:".format(len(os.listdir(healthy_trn_dir))))
print("{} Infected valid images:".format(len(os.listdir(infected_valid_dir))))
print("{} Uninfected valid images:".format(len(os.listdir(healthy_valid_dir))))
print("{} Infected testing images:".format(len(os.listdir(infected_test_dir))))
print("{} Uninfected testing images:".format(len(os.listdir(healthy_test_dir))))

```

Exploratory Data Analysis

Train

```

infected_trn_fpaths = [os.path.join(infected_trn_dir, fpath) for fpath in os.listdir(infected_trn_dir)]
healthy_trn_fpaths = [os.path.join(healthy_trn_dir, fpath) for fpath in os.listdir(healthy_trn_dir)]

```

Valid

```

infected_valid_fpaths = [os.path.join(infected_valid_dir, fpath) for fpath in os.listdir(infected_valid_dir)]
healthy_valid_fpaths = [os.path.join(healthy_valid_dir, fpath) for fpath in os.listdir(healthy_valid_dir)]

```

Test

```

infected_test_fpaths = [os.path.join(infected_test_dir, fpath) for fpath in os.listdir(infected_test_dir)]
healthy_test_fpaths = [os.path.join(healthy_test_dir, fpath) for fpath in os.listdir(healthy_test_dir)]

```

```

def get_img_shape(idx, img, total_num_images):

```

```

    if idx%2000 ==0 or idx == (total_num_images-1):
        print("working on img {}".format(idx))
    return cv2.imread(img).shape

```

```

data_inp = [(idx, img, len(infected_trn_fpaths + healthy_trn_fpaths)) for idx, img in enumerate(infected_trn_fpaths
+ healthy_trn_fpaths)]

```

```

train_img_dims_map = list(map(get_img_shape, [input[0] for input in data_inp],
    [input[1] for input in data_inp],
    [input[2] for input in data_inp]))

```

```

print('Min Dimensions:      {}'.format(np.min(train_img_dims_map, axis=0)))
print('Avg Dimensions:      {}'.format(np.mean(train_img_dims_map, axis=0)))
print('Median Dimensions:   {}'.format(np.median(train_img_dims_map, axis=0)))
print('Most Frequent Dimensions: {}'.format(stats.mode(train_img_dims_map, axis=0)[0]))
print('Max Dimensions:      {}'.format(np.max(train_img_dims_map, axis=0)))

```

```
infected_trn_samples = random.sample(infected_trn_fpaths, 5)
healthy_trn_samples = random.sample(healthy_trn_fpaths, 5)
```

```
fig=plt.figure(figsize=(28,14))
columns=5
rows=1
for i in range(1, columns*rows +1):
    fig.add_subplot(rows, columns, i)
    plt.imshow(mpimg.imread(infected_trn_samples[i-1]))
    plt.axis('off')
    plt.title('Infected', fontsize=32)
plt.show()
```

```
fig=plt.figure(figsize=(28,14))
columns=5
rows=1
for i in range(1, columns*rows +1):
    fig.add_subplot(rows, columns, i)
    plt.imshow(mpimg.imread(healthy_trn_samples[i-1]))
    plt.axis('off')
    plt.title('Healthy', fontsize=32)
plt.show()
```

Data Augmentation and Resizing Images

```
train_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1./255.,
    horizontal_flip=0.4,
    vertical_flip=0.4,
    rotation_range=40,
    shear_range=0.2,
    width_shift_range=0.4,
    height_shift_range=0.4,
    fill_mode='nearest')
valid_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1.0/255.)
test_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1.0/255.)
```

```
train_generator = train_datagen.flow_from_directory(train_dir,
    batch_size=32,
    target_size=(128,128),
    class_mode='categorical',
    shuffle=True,
    seed=42,
    color_mode='rgb')
```

```
valid_generator = valid_datagen.flow_from_directory(valid_dir,
    batch_size=32,
    target_size=(128, 128),
    class_mode='categorical',
    shuffle=True,
    seed=42,
    color_mode='rgb')
```

```
class_labels = train_generator.class_indices
class_names = {value:key for (key, value) in class_labels.items()}
```

Instantiate VGG19 model with weights from Imagenet without the calssifier at the top

```

base_model = VGG19(input_shape = (128,128,3),
                  include_top = False,
                  weights = 'imagenet')
# Freeze the ConvNet to avoid weight updates
for layer in base_model.layers:
    layer.trainable=False

x = base_model.output
flat=Flatten()(x)

# Add a classifier - a fully connected dense layers
class_1 = Dense(4608, activation='relu')(flat)
drop_out = Dropout(0.2)(class_1)
class_2 = Dense(1152, activation='relu')(drop_out)
output = Dense(2, activation='softmax')(class_2)

# Bake a model
model_01 = Model(base_model.inputs, output)
model_01.summary()

# Call backs
filepath = 'best_model.h5'
es = EarlyStopping(monitor='val_loss', verbose=1, mode='min', patience=4)
cp = ModelCheckpoint(filepath, monitor='val_loss', verbose=1, save_best_only=True,
                    save_weights_only=False, mode='auto', save_freq='epoch')
lrr = ReduceLROnPlateau(monitor='val_accuracy',patience=3,verbose=1,factor=0.5,min_lr=0.0001)

# Define an optimizer
sgd = SGD(lr=.0001, decay=1e-6, momentum=0.9, nesterov=True)

# Compile the model
model_01.compile(loss="categorical_crossentropy", optimizer=sgd, metrics=["accuracy"])

# Plot performance
fig, (ax1,ax2) = plt.subplots(nrows=1, ncols=2, figsize=(12,6))
fig.suptitle("Model Training(Frozen CNN)", fontsize=20)
max_epoch = len(history_01.history['accuracy'])+1
epochs_list = list(range(1, max_epoch))

ax1.plot(epochs_list, history_01.history['accuracy'], color='b', linestyle='-', label='Training Data')
ax1.plot(epochs_list, history_01.history['val_accuracy'], color='r', linestyle='-', label='Validation Data')
ax1.set_title("Training Accuracy", fontsize=14)
ax1.set_xlabel('Epochs', fontsize=14)
ax1.set_ylabel('Accuracy', fontsize=14)
ax1.legend(frameon=False, loc='lower center', ncol=2)

ax2.plot(epochs_list, history_01.history['loss'], color='b', linestyle='-', label='Training Data')
ax2.plot(epochs_list, history_01.history['val_loss'], color='r', linestyle='-', label='Validation Data')
ax2.set_title("Training Loss", fontsize=14)
ax2.set_xlabel('Epochs', fontsize=14)
ax2.set_ylabel('Loss', fontsize=14)
ax2.legend(frameon=False, loc='upper center', ncol=2)

# Load the saved model
model_03.load_weights('model_weights/vgg_unfrozen.h5')
# Evaluate the model on the hold out validation and test datasets

```

```

vgg_val_eval_03 = model_03.evaluate_generator(valid_generator)
vgg_test_eval_03 = model_03.evaluate_generator(test_generator)

print('Validation loss   :{0:.2f}'.format(vgg_val_eval_03[0]))
print('Validation accuracy :{0:.2f}'.format(vgg_val_eval_03[1]))
print('Test loss         :{0:.2f}'.format(vgg_test_eval_03[0]))
print('Test accuracy    :{0:.2f}'.format(vgg_test_eval_03[1]))

filenames = test_generator.filenames
nb_samples = len(filenames)
vgg_predictions_03 = model_03.predict_generator(test_generator,
                                               steps = nb_samples,
                                               verbose=1)
vgg_pred_labels_03 = np.argmax(vgg_predictions_03, axis=1)

# Classification Report
print(classification_report(test_generator.classes, vgg_pred_labels_03,
                           target_names=['healthy', 'infected']))
vgg_conf_mat_03 = pd.DataFrame(confusion_matrix(test_generator.classes, vgg_pred_labels_03),
                              index=['healthy', 'infected'],
                              columns=['healthy', 'infected'])

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(5,5))

sns.heatmap(vgg_conf_mat_03, annot=True, fmt=".1f", linewidths=0.5, square=True, cmap='Blues_r')
ax.set_ylabel("Actual Label", fontsize=14)
ax.set_xlabel("Predicted Label", fontsize=14)
all_sample_title="Accuracy Score: {0:.2f}".format(vgg_test_eval_03[1])
ax.set_title(all_sample_title, size=15)
ax.set_ylim(len(vgg_conf_mat_03)-0.05, -0.05)
plt.tight_layout()

```